

Velocity Distribution and Minimal Information from Constraints

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In previous notes, we argued that the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is consistent with two constraints: $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$. There are many $\{ p(e_i) \}$ solutions to these constraints, yet one appears in nature (say for an ideal gas). We suggested that one could find a unique minimal information $\{ p(e_i) \}$ by postulating a function G (entropy) such that $dG = \sum_i c_i d(\text{constraints}) = 0$. We also showed that such an approach yields $p(e_1)p(e_2)=p(e_3)p(e_4)$ with $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$, i.e. it is directly linked with conservation if in fact there are physical two body collisions. (This is not always the case as in the 2-level atom.)

One might try to apply the above situation to a one-dimensional momentum (i.e. a velocity distribution in the nonrelativistic case). One has the constraints: $\sum_i p(p_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i p_i p(p_i) = 0$ as well as two body collisions which conserve momentum. This seems like an ideal candidate for the approach, but unfortunately, the minimal information $p(p_i)$ based on differentials of constraints yields $p(p_i) = C \exp(-c p_i)$. This means that p_i and $-p_i$ do not have the same probability. Furthermore, this result cannot yield $\sum_i p(p_i) p_i = 0$. Thus, it seems that there is different information in this problem. In particular, $p(p_i) = p(-p_i)$ seems to be extra information present. If one tries changing the constraint to: $\sum_i (\text{for } p_i > 0) p_i p(p_i) = P_{total}$ (positive), then one cannot know P_{total} a priori for the following reason. Imagine that one has N particles. All but two are at rest, one has e_1, p_1 and the other $e_1, -p_1$. The total energy is $2e_1$ and the average energy is always $2e_1/N$ so when equilibrium occurs: $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave} = 2e_1/N$. On the other hand, p_{total} is 0 and this also holds for equilibrium, but P_{total} (positive) is not p_1 , it changes and one has no idea of its value. Thus, a priori, it seems that in the velocity case, one has to go with an energy constraint which is a $v \cdot v \cdot m$ constraint. In such a case, the minimal information differentials of constraints works because $v \cdot v$ ensures $p(p_i) = p(-p_i)$ automatically, which seems to be the only extra information causing problems.

Minimal Information From Constraints

In previous notes, we developed a minimal information based on differentials of constraints procedure to derive the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. We started with the constraints:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad ((1a)) \quad \sum_i f(e_i) p(e_i) = F \quad ((1b))$$

and noted that there are multiple $\{ p(e_i) \}$ solutions consistent with ((1a)) and ((1b)). One might seek a particular unique solution based on the idea that the only information available is in the constraints. One may then introduce a function (entropy):

$$G = \sum_i p(e_i) h(p(e_i)) \quad \text{with } h(p(e_i)) = -f(e_i)/T \quad ((2)) \quad \text{and use:}$$

$$dG = 0 = \sum_i c_i d(\text{constraints}) \quad ((3))$$

Then: $h(p(e_i)) = -f(e_i)/T$ and $p(e_i) df/dp(e_i) = 1$ leading to: $p(e_i) = C \exp(-f(e_i)/T)$ ((4))

We have further shown in previous notes that the above procedure guarantees:

$$p(f(e_1)) p(f(e_2)) = p(f(e_3)) p(f(e_4)) \text{ and } f(e_1)+f(e_2)=f(e_3)+f(e_4) \quad ((5))$$

For ((5)) to be useful, one must have two body scattering in the problem. For a two energy level atom, one does not have this 2-body scattering, but still has a MB distribution for $f(e_i)=e_i$. Note, the above approach works for any $f(e_i)$ as long as it is a priori information.

Application to a 1-Dimensional Momentum Problem

The above recipe seems ideal for the obtaining a velocity/momentum distribution based on the constraints:

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p_i p(\pi_i) = 0 \text{ and Sum over } i \text{ } p(\pi_i) = 1 \quad ((6))$$

In such a case, two body scattering exists in an ideal gas and one knows that there is momentum conservation, i.e ((5)) holds.

$$\text{Applying the above procedure, however, yields: } p(\pi_i) = C \exp(-b \pi_i) \quad ((7))$$

In other words: $p(\pi_i) \neq p(-\pi_i)$ ((8)) To make matters worse, ((7)) cannot satisfy:

$$((6)) \text{ because: Sum over } \pi_i > 0 \text{ } \pi_i (\exp(-b\pi_i) - \exp(b\pi_i)) \quad ((8)) \text{ cannot be 0.}$$

For $b > 0$, $\exp(b\pi_i) > 1$, being 1 for $\pi_i = 0$. Thus, $\exp(-b\pi_i)$ is less than this value and so there is no possible way for ((6)) to be satisfied for $\pi_i > 0$ used in ((8)).

The conclusion seems to be that the information of the constraints is not fully describing the problem. In particular, one has the condition:

$$p(\pi_i) = p(-\pi_i) \text{ and this seems to be a separate condition which must hold } \quad ((9))$$

One may change the constraints ((6)) assuming ((9)) applies, but this yields:

$$\text{Sum over } \pi_i > 0 \text{ } p(\pi_i) = .5 \text{ and Sum over } \pi_i > 0 \text{ } \pi_i p(\pi_i) = P_{\text{total positive}} \quad ((10))$$

One should then be able to solve for $p(e_i)$, but the problem is that $P_{\text{total positive}}$ is not an a priori constraint and cannot be used. To see this, consider N particles in a box. Two have energy and momentum: e_1, p_1 and $e_1, -p_1$ and the others are at rest. The total energy is $2e_1$ and this cannot change regardless of the distribution which appears. Thus, $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i p(e_i) = E_{\text{ave}} = 2e_1/N$ still holds when equilibrium occurs, but such a condition does not follow for $P_{\text{total positive}}$ and p_1 will change. Thus, it is only the energy which may be used as the a priori

constraint and this leads to a $.5m v^2$ constraint in terms of velocity. One may use the minimal information approach for the variable v , but then use $f(v) = .5m v^2$ (1-dimension) and the procedure then leads to a Gaussian:

$$p(e_i) = C \exp(-.5mv^2/T) \quad ((11))$$

Basically, the v^2 constraint ensures that $p(p_i) = p(-p_i)$ and so this is not an independent condition any longer.

Conclusion

In conclusion, even if $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i f(e_i) p(e_i) = F$ constraints exist in a problem, there may be other hidden a priori constraints which stop one from using the first two in a minimal information based on differentials of constraints approach. We suggest that this is what happens for a velocity distribution. Even though total momentum, and so average momentum, must be zero and there is conservation of momentum, one must have $p(p_i) = p(-p_i)$ and this is not forced by the minimal information approach for a linear v constraint. Furthermore, if one focuses on only the positive p average, one does not know this value a priori, while the average energy is a constraint. Thus, one is forced to use $f(v) = .5mv^2$ (1-D) as the constraint in a minimal information based on differentials approach because $.5mv^2$ automatically enforces $p(p_i) = p(-p_i)$, we argue and so it is no longer an independent condition.